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Vector Spin of subatomic particles and Antigravity

Gravity is a phenomenon of bending the space-time fabric when any kind of mass spins in the ether of the universe. If the vector spin of subatomic particles can be reversed and directed, absolute antigravity and warp drives can be generated.

The spin equation is classified as a Systematic Invention Unit.